

However, Benton and Elton (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 1213) showed that powdered silica dissolved in aqueous HCl solutions due to the formation of colloidal silica on the surface. The ξ -potential was found to amount to -90.5 mv. This result was obtained from conductivity measurements which indicated an increase upon the addition of silica. These results, although contradicting our findings, show that the process taking place with powdered silica is not necessarily the same as that with low-molecular silica. If silica is charged negatively in Benton and Elton's sense, it should migrate in the electric current, which is not the case. It seems quite probable that the dehydration of low-molecular silica in solution affects the adsorption energies of the H^+ and Cl^- ions in such a manner as to become equal. If this is true, low-molecular silica will adsorb H^+ as well as Cl^- ions with equal probability. This assumption lends itself to explain the fact that silica does not move in the electric current and that solutions containing low-molecular silica possess a lower conductance than the corresponding solutions of acidified sodium hydroxide.

ALEXANDRIA UNIVERSITY,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
ALEXANDRIA, EGYPT.

Received June 14, 1956.

[*Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Vol. **34**, No. 6, 1956]

HYDROCHLORIC ACID SOLUTIONS CONTAINING SILICA. PART II. POTENTIOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS

By HUSSEIN SADEK AND SASSON ABOUHAROUN

pCl measurements with the help of the silver chloride electrode were carried out at 25° on solutions containing low-molecular silica in the concentration range of 0.02–0.056 mole per litre. The results indicate that adsorption is taking place in these solutions. An equation has been developed which fits in with the experimental data. p_H values run in a parallel manner.

In an earlier communication by one of us (Sadek, this *Journal*, 1952, **29**, 507) pCl measurements on acidified sodium metasilicate solutions were reported. The results indicate a pronounced increase in pCl values over those calculated on the assumption that the Cl^- ions are totally free but nearer to those calculated on the basis of combination of one mole HCl per mole SiO_2 , and confirm the idea of compound formation between silica and HCl (Lösenbeck, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1922, **16**, 27; Tourky, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1939, **240**, 198). In Part I of this series (Sadek and Abouharoun, this *issue*, p. 443) it has been observed that silica behaves as a non-electrolyte and that adsorption of ions by low-molecular silica is responsible for the decrease on conductance and of the transport number of the Cl^- ion below the corresponding value in solutions, void of silica. If this view is correct, one should find an increase in p_H and pCl values as the concentration of silica increases in the the solution. In this communication potentiometric

measurements of the H^+ and Cl^- ions have been made and the results confirm the idea of adsorption of these ions by freshly formed low-molecular silica.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of alkali silicate solutions I, II, III and IV and of 0.1N-HCl was described in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

p_H measurements were carried out with the help of a Beckman p_H -meter (model H). The instrument was standardised before use by means of a potassium biphthalate buffer of p_H 4.

p_{Cl} measurements were determined with the help of the silver-silver chloride electrode, prepared according to MacInnes and Parker (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **37**, 1445). Several such electrodes were prepared and those which gave zero potential against each other, when immersed in dilute HCl solution, were chosen for the determination of the Cl^- ion activity. The selected electrodes were tested before use in the silica-containing solutions by immersion in HCl solutions of known activities. The data of Lewis and Randall ("Thermodynamics and the Free Energy of Chemical Substances", McGraw Hill, 1923, p. 336) were plotted on a large scale such that the mean activity of the prepared solutions could be easily interpolated. The HCl solutions were obtained from the constant boiling acid by weight dilution. Table I shows the behaviour of the best electrodes. The cell which was used could be represented as :

All potentiometric measurements were carried out in a thermostat adjusted at 25°.

TABLE I

The standard potential of the AgCl, Ag electrode.

<i>m.</i>	<i>E</i> cell.	<i>E</i> ° AgCl, Ag.	<i>m.</i>	<i>E</i> cell.	<i>E</i> ° AgCl, Ag.
0.11850	0.0473 v	0.2288 v	0.02370	0.0860 v	0.2272 v
0.05925	0.0652	0.2289	0.01185	0.1058	0.2294
0.04740	0.0700	0.2287	0.00593	0.1228	0.2287

Mean : 0.2286 v

It can be seen that the average value of E° is about 6 mv higher than the accepted value. Lewis and Randall (*loc. cit.*) report 0.2234 v; Scatchard (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 641) gave 0.2223 v, while Randall and Young (*ibid.*, 1928, **50**, 989) found 0.2221 v. The deviation is definitely due to the inclusion of a liquid junction potential across the saturated ammonium nitrate-agar salt bridge. According to Afanasiev (*ibid.*, 1930, **52**, 3477) silver chloride electrodes exhibit variation in the value of their standard potentials because of the lack of uniform method of electrode preparation; the various manipulatory conditions have a marked effect on the characteristics of the surfaces of silver halides and, hence, they have different potentials. In spite of this discrepancy, the selected electrodes have been used since relative rather than absolute values are more important in the solutions containing silica.

DISCUSSION

p_H Measurements.—Fig. 1 shows the titration curves of 25 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-HCl solution against various alkali silicate solutions containing increasing amounts of silica. It is

quite remarkable to find that the curves do not coincide on each other, although these solutions are equinormal with respect to their sodium hydroxide content. The departure from the dotted curve for sodium hydroxide is therefore due to the interference of low-molecular silica. For a given quantity of alkali added, the p_H is higher, the higher the concentration of silica in the reagent. This result is in harmony with earlier findings that adsorption is prevailing in these solutions. The p_H increases as the H^+ ions are removed from solution by adsorption.

One must bear in mind that low-molecular silica in these solutions behaves as a non-electrolyte formed by the suppression of ionisation of silicic acid in the presence of H^+ ions. The suppressed acid, as an ion-pair, would be expected to attract a number of water molecules around it on account of its high polarity (Sadek, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 619). This effect would affect the p_H in the opposite direction, thus causing a decrease (Sadek and Zayan, *ibid.*, 1953, 30, 823). The above measurements indicate that in solutions near the end-point (above 85% neutralisation), the adsorption effect outweighs the solvation effect. This conclusion supports the early findings of the decrease in conductance as the concentration of silica increases.

pCl Measurements.—Equilibrium values were always obtained within 30 minutes from immersion of the silver-silver chloride electrode, and then they began to change with time. Table II shows the pCl values obtained from several measurements on mixtures containing increasing amounts of silica and the same total concentration of Cl^- ions. These mixtures were prepared by adding, with constant stirring, varying aliquots of alkali silicate (solution I, II, III or IV) to 25 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-HCl and diluting the mixture to 50 c.c. in a standard volumetric flask. The mixtures denoted by the symbols A, B, C, D and E represent those made by the addition of 20, 21, 22, 23 and 24 c.c. of alkali silicate respectively.

TABLE II

Mixture.	Soln. I+HCl.		Soln. II+HCl.		Soln. III+HCl		Soln. IV+HCl.	
	pCl .	Mole $SiO_2/l.$	pCl .	Mole $SiO_2/l.$	pCl .	Mole $SiO_2/l.$	pCl .	Mole $SiO_2/l.$
A	1.697	0.020	1.748	0.0300	1.792	0.040	1.826	0.047
B	1.704	0.021	1.751	0.0315	1.799	0.042	1.833	0.049
C	1.706	0.022	1.760	0.0330	1.811	0.044	1.843	0.0513
D	1.716	0.023	1.762	0.0345	1.816	0.046	1.857	0.054
E	1.721	0.024	1.768	0.0360	1.825	0.048	1.873	0.056

Fig. 2 shows a plot of pCl against $(2 + \log SiO_2)$. The relation is quite linear at low concentration of silica and shows a more rapid increase at higher concentrations. It

FIG. 2

can also be seen that over the limited range of any one of the four sets a linear relation can be found as was shown previously (Sadek, *loc. cit.*). In order to gain a deeper insight into the nature of these solutions, a calculation of the Cl^- ions adsorbed was made. For comparison several measurements of the pCl value obtained for the corresponding solutions prepared by the addition of $NaOH$ to HCl were carried out. The average value was 1.633 ± 0.005 . This corresponds to a chloride ion activity of 0.02328 . Table III shows the amounts of Cl^- ions adsorbed per mole SiO_2 .

TABLE III

Mixture.	$a_{Cl}(obs.)$.	$a_{Cl}(ad.)$.	$a_{Cl}(ad.)/SiO_2$.	$a_{Cl}(obs.)$.	$a_{Cl}(ad.)$.	$a_{Cl}(ad.)/SiO_2$.
Solution I+HCl.			Solution II+HCl.			
A	0.02009	0.00319	0.160	0.01786	0.00542	0.180
B	0.01977	0.00351	0.167	0.01774	0.00554	0.176
C	0.01968	0.00360	0.164	0.01738	0.00590	0.179
D	0.01950	0.00378	0.164	0.01730	0.00598	0.173
E	0.01901	0.00427	0.178	0.01706	0.00622	0.173
		Mean : 0.166			Mean : 0.176	
Solution III+HCl.			Solution IV+HCl.			
A	0.01614	0.00714	0.152	0.01493	0.00835	0.209
B	0.01589	0.00739	0.151	0.01461	0.00859	0.205
C	0.01545	0.00783	0.153	0.01435	0.00893	0.203
D	0.01531	0.00797	0.148	0.01390	0.00938	0.204
E	0.01496	0.00832	0.149	0.01340	0.00988	0.206
		Mean : 0.151			Mean : 0.205	

It can be seen that the amount of Cl^- adsorbed per mole SiO_2 is almost constant, having an average value of 0.175.

If one assumes that the amount of Cl^- adsorbed $\{Cl(ad)\}$ is proportional to the Cl^- ion concentration originally present $\{Cl(o)\}$ and to the silica content, one can write the relation,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cl(ad)} &= k \text{Cl(o)} (\text{SiO}_2)^n \\ \text{also } \text{Cl(free)} &= \text{Cl(o)} - \text{Cl(ad)} \\ &= \text{Cl(o)} [1 - k(\text{SiO}_2)^n] \\ \text{therefore } p\text{Cl} &= p\text{Cl(o)} - \log [1 - k(\text{SiO}_2)^n]. \\ \text{Assuming that } k (\text{SiO}_2)^n < 1, \text{ one gets} \\ p\text{Cl} &= p\text{Cl(o)} + k(\text{SiO}_2)^n. \end{aligned}$$

By plotting $\log [p\text{Cl} - p\text{Cl(o)}]$ against $\log (\text{SiO}_2)$ a straight line was obtained from the slope and intercept of which the values of k and n were found to be 4.0 and 1.2 respectively. Therefore, over the range of silica concentration 0.02–0.056 mole per litre, the relation $p\text{Cl} = 1.633 + 4 (\text{SiO}_2)^{1.2}$ is valid. The derivation of the above relation is based on the assumption that the state of aggregation of low-molecular silica is the same in all the mixtures and that the activity coefficient is not influenced by the presence of silica. It is concluded that the presence of these discrete charges on the molecule of silica does not give it enough mobility to be detected analytically. Besides, these surface charges seem to be the initial stage in the coagulation process in Greenberg and Sinclair's sense (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 435).

ALEXANDRIA UNIVERSITY,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
ALEXANDRIA, EGYPT.

Received June 14, 1956.